

Preparation and Antitubercular Activity of Some 1-(4-Amino-3,5-dibromo)-2-benzalhydrazine and 1-[4-(Phenylthioureido-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazines

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Several 1-(4-amino-3,5-dibromo)-2-benzalhydrazine and 1-[4-(phenylthioureido-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazines have been prepared and screened for their antitubercular activity against $H_{37}R_v$ strain.

THIOUREA derivatives are known to possess antitubercular¹, antibacterial and other biological activities²⁻⁷. Taxonomic similarity between *Mycobacteria* and fungi prompted to test the effect of some known antifungal agents against *M. tuberculosis in vitro*⁸. Among the compounds tested only certain thioureas showed tuberculostatic activity *in vitro*.

Hydrazones have been found to possess antibacterial⁹, antifungal¹⁰ and insecticidal¹¹ activities. Schiff bases are known to exhibit anticancer and antitubercular activities¹²⁻¹³.

The present communication deals with the preparation and pharmacological studies of some 1-(4-amino-3,5-dibromo)-2-benzalhydrazine (I) and 1-[4-(phenylthioureido-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazines (II) have been prepared from various 1-(4-amino-3,5-dibromo)-2-benzalhydrazines by condensation of phenylisothiocyanate and tested against $H_{37}R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Scheme 1
Where R = Different aromatic moiety.

The synthetic sequence of the title compounds is presented in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds synthesised were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structure of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis and ir spectra (KBr) using Spectromom 2000 spectrophotometer. The ir spectra of the thiourea of the title compounds show band at 1380 cm^{-1} due to -NH-CS-NH- linkage and at 3200 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of stretching frequency of -OH of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

4-Amino-3,5-dibromobenzoic acid hydrazide: 4-Amino-3,5-dibromo benzoic acid hydrazide was prepared by the reported method¹⁴.

1-(4-Amino-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (I): To the solution of 4-amino-3,5-dibromo benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 28 ml) was added benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 15 ml) and the content kept for 24 h at room temperature. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%) to yield the product (62%), m.p. 245° (Found: N, 10.79%. $C_{14}H_{12}Br_2N_2O$ requires N, 10.58%).

1-[4-(Phenylthioureido)-3,5-dibromobenzoyl]-2-benzalhydrazine (II): To the solution of 1-(4-amino-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 30 ml) was added phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 20 ml) and the contents refluxed for 45 min, cooled and filtered. The solid so obtained was washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol (95%) to yield the product (82%), m.p. 230° (Found: N, 10.75; S, 6.23%. $C_{21}H_{16}Br_2N_4OS$ requires N, 10.53; S, 6.02%).

Antimycobacterial screening: The *in vitro* antitubercular activity of the compounds I and II have been studied at 0, 5 and $30\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration

TABLE 1—DATA OF 1-(4-AMINO-3,5-DIBROMOBENZOYL-2-BENZALHYDRAZINE (I)

Sl. no.	R	M. p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$		
				0	5	30
1.	Phenyl	245	62	—	—	—
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	285	70	—	—	—
3.	3-Chlorophenyl	220	64	—	—	+
4.	3-Nitrophenyl	260	68	—	—	—
5.	4-Nitrophenyl	320	59	—	—	+
6.	4-Methoxyphenyl	240	65	—	—	+
7.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	280	67	—	—	+
8.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxy phenyl	281	63	—	+	+
9.	3,4-Methylenedioxy phenyl	270	72	—	+	+
10.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy phenyl	244	73	—	—	—
11.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	280	66	—	—	—
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	248	71	—	—	—

All compounds gave satisfactory C, N, S analyses.

+ Active.

— Not active.

TABLE 2—DATA OF 1-[4-(PHENYL THIOUREIDO-3,5-DIBROMO BENZOYL)]-2-SUBSTITUTED-BENZALHYDRAZINE (II)

Sl. no.	R	M. p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$		
				0	5	30
1.	Phenyl	230	82	—	—	—
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	225	81	—	—	+
3.	3-Chlorophenyl	203	78	—	—	+
4.	3-Nitrophenyl	223	86	—	—	—
5.	4-Nitrophenyl	146	72	—	—	—
6.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	246	80	—	—	+
7.	4-Methoxyphenyl	179	75	—	—	+
8.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	250	83	—	—	+
9.	3,4-Methylenedioxy phenyl	144	88	—	—	+
10.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	196	72	—	—	+
11.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxy phenyl	138	76	—	—	+
12.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy phenyl	180	84	—	—	+

Notes same as in Table 1.

using dimethylformamide as solvent against $H_{37}B_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* utilising Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium (4 ml). The procedure was duplicated.

The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

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